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With this thought we hereby present you,
International Journal of Legal Enforcement

Analysis of caste system

-J. Janat Sharlee

Introduction

The cast system which in India can be traced as an oldest form of sociological structure in a human history around the global. The system one used for a organizational structure of a society but later utilize by some evil intended person as the prima source of defecation and modus operandi of the vote bank for elections across the country. Basically, cast is conferred upon the occupation therefore it is by right of birth in a globalized world cast differentiation plays A dominant role it's for many times ends upon the massacre and for many times honor killing the influence of egatrialianism can be traced as bases for this differentiation and also political game uses the caste differentiation as the powerful weapon. The caste system prevails in the ancient times and how it stands to a discrimination can be found critically analysis in this paper.

DEFINITION:

According to MAZUMDAR AND MADAN” caste is a closed class i.e. class refers to people based on property, business, occupation i.e. one can't change his own caste system by can change the class system& can be a member of many classes at the same time. You belong to a caste by birth & can't change it later & one has is follow the set rules ®ulations & gets punishment on their violation & one can even be thrown out of his caste i.e. if one dares to go out of his caste he can never return. In class one many change it with effort like in a illiterate class one can become literate &therefore go over to the literate class i.e. caste is hereditary in nature &once born in a caste one can't change it¹.

According to HERBERT KISLEY” class is a collection of families or group of families bearing a common name which usually denotes or its associated with a specific occupation, calming descent from a mythical ancestor, human or divine, professing to follow the same heredity callings ®arded by those who are competent to give an opinion as forming a single homogenous communities.”²

¹ <http://www.civildserviceindia.com/subject/sociology/notes/castesystem.html>, Retrieved on June 14, 2020

² <http://www.civildserviceindia.com/subject/sociology/notes/castesystem.html> Retrieved on June 15, 2020

ORIGIN OF CASTE SYSTEM:

According to the social historical theory, the origin of CASTE SYSTEM finds its origin in the arrival of Aryans in India. The Aryans organized themselves in three groups. caste system was found in 1500bc-1000bc. There are different theories of regarding the caste system in India. The religious theory claims that the VARANS were created from the body of the BRAHMA, the creator of the world. The BRAHMANAS were created from his naval, the KSHATRIYAS from his hand, the VAISHYAS from his thighs and the SUDRAS from his feet. The remaining members are treated like a slave. The Aryans organized themselves in three groups.

WAARIORS, later they called as rajanya, and then they changed the name as KSHATRIYAAS. PRIESTS, now a days they are usually called as brahmans. There are some conflict based on there leadership.³ Perspectives for the origin is for two types i.e. ancient and medieval India, which focus on either ideological factor or on socio economic factors. The first school is focused on the religious anthropology and disregarded other historical evidence as secondary to or derivative of this tradition⁴. In ancient days there are RITUAL KINGSHIP MODEL forge aspects of the later Indian caste system may originate from the ritual kingship system prior to the arrival of Brahmanism, Buddhism and Jainism in India. This system is formed in India in sixth century.⁵

JATHIS nowadays caste is exposed in the world of Jathi. “a professor of philosophy and religious studies, states that it is impossible to determine how and why the jathi came into existence.⁶ according to Bisham” ancient Indian literature refers often to varnas, but hardly if ever to jathis as a system of group within the Varnas. He concludes that” if caste is defined as a system of group within the class, which are normally endogamous, commensal and craft exclusive, we have no real evidence of its existence until comparatively late times.⁷

INFLUENCE ON RELIGION:

Caste is the upper and lower segments of people, created by the humans in early society formation by the then intellectual, who were majority stake holders of the society.

³³ <http://m.hindustantimes.com/india/originofcastesystem>, Retrieved on June 16 2020

⁴ Gupta, Dipankar (2000), interrogating caste verified on the date of June 12, 2020

⁵ Geoffrey Samuel “the origin of yoga and tantric religions to the thirteenth century” established by Cambridge university press.

⁶ Fowler, jeaneane (1997) Hinduism belief and practices-published by Sussex academic press pg;23-24 on the date of june12 2020

⁷ Basham, wonder that was India (1954) a survey of the culture of the Indian sub continent before the coming of muslims.pg 148 viewed on june12 2020.

RELIGION is the belief of race practice that ones ancestor started to fellow in belief or rituals. In Hindu influence in caste system is expressed in VARAN.it was named by romances a Sanskrit world it means type, color, class etc. It used to refer the social classes in Hindu MANUSMRITI.⁸the varnas classified into four types.

- 1) SHUDRAS
- 2) VAISHYAS
- 3) KSHATRIYAS
- 4) BRAHMINS, varnas are also called as savanna.

BRAHMINS:

Brahmins the seers, the reflective ones, the priest.

- a. The intellectual and spiritual leaders.
- b. In our society, they would correspond to the philosophers, religious leaders, and teachers

KSHATRIYAS:

They born administrators formally nobles, Rajas, warriors.

- a. The protectors of society.
- b. In our society, the politicians, police, and the military.

VAISYAS:

The producers, the craftsmen, artisans, farmers.

- a. the skillful producers of material things.
- b.in our society, the merchants.

Shudras they are followers and maintenance people. They so called menial workers or hard laborers.⁹The Sanskrit term varna is derived from the root.it means “to cover, to envelop, count, classify consider, describe or choose”. The word Rigveda where it means “color, outward appearance, exterior form, figure or shape”¹⁰.

BUDDHIST PERIOD:

Ancient Buddhist text mention varna system in south Asia, but the details suggest that it was a non-rigid, flexible and with characteristics devoid of features of a social stratification system.¹¹Tonawanda adds that it is impossible to reduce the requirement for

⁸ Malik jamal (2005).religious pluralism in south asia and Europe.oxfordukkk;oxford university press.pg no 48.dated on June 13 2020.

⁹ Philosophy 312:oriental philosophy Hinduism :variefed on the date of June 14 2020

¹⁰ Krishna charitra by bankim Chandra chottopadhyay.bengal renaissance DATED ON June 13, 2020

¹¹Masefield,peter(2008).divine revelation in pali Buddhism. Routledge.pg 146-154.

being a Brahmin any further, because” for wisdom is purified by morality, and morality is purified by wisdom; where one is ,the other is, the moral man has wisdom and the wise man has morality, and the combination of morality and wisdom is called the highest thing in world”¹²Brian Black and Dean Patton state Tonawanda admits after this, “we only know this much Gautama; it would be well if revered Gautama would explain meaning of the two.”¹³

JAINISM:

Jainism is different to Buddhism in its ascetic belief. Both these religions emphasize nonviolence, but nonviolence is the main core in Jainism. Mahavira just like Buddha isn't the first prophet of his religion. In Jainism like Buddhism there is a belief in reincarnation which eventually leads to liberation.¹⁴ The god of Jainism does not believe in god as a creator, survivor, and destroyer of the universe. However Jainism does believe in god ,not as a creator, but as a perfect being they do not have one god but Jain gods are innumerable and their numbers are continuously increasing as more living beings attain liberation. It holds that one must abandon all violent activity and that without such a commitment to nonviolence all religious behavior is worthless.¹⁵

SIKHISM:

Although the Sikh gurus criticized the hierarchy of the caste system, one does exist in Sikh community. According to surrenders, Jodoka, the Sikh religion does not advocate discrimination against any caste or creed, however, in practice, Sikhs belonging to the landowning dominant caste have not shed all their prejudices against the Dalits. In 1953, the government of India acceded to the demand of the Sikh leader, Tara Singh, to include Sikh caste of the converted untouchables in the list of scheduled caste. In the Shiroma gurdwara paranda committee, 20 of the 140 seats are reserved for low caste Sikhs.¹⁶

The Sikh literature from the Islamic rule and British colonial era mentions varna as varna, and jathi as Zat or Zat Biradari. Eleanor Nesbitt, a professor of religion and author of books on Sikhism, states that the varna is described as a class system ,while Zat has some caste system features in Sikh literature.¹⁷

CHRISTIANS:

¹² Walshe, Maurice (1995) The long discourses of the Buddha: a translation of the Dighi nikayas. Boston: Wisdom publications. pg 129-131 dated on June 14, 2020

¹³ Black, Brian; Patton, Dean Laurie (2015). Dialogue in early South Asian religions: Hindu, Buddhist, and Jain traditions. pg. no. 245-246 dated on June 14, 2020

¹⁴ <http://www.qcc.cuny.edu>ppecorino.48748>, Retrieved on June 18 2020

¹⁵ Dundas, Paul (2002), The Jains (second ed.) pg. no 160

¹⁶ Puri, Harish K. (2004), Dalits in regional context. pg no 214 dated on 17 June 2020

¹⁷ Nesbitt, Eleanor (2005). Sikhism a very short introduction .Oxford; New York; pg. no 116-117.

Social stratification is found among the Christians in India based on caste as well as by their denomination and location. The caste distinction is based on their caste at the time that they or their ancestors converted to Christianity since the 16th century, they typically do not intermarry, and sit separately during prayers in church.¹⁸

DUNCAN FORRESTER observes that “nowhere else in India is there a large and ancient Christian community which has in time immemorial been accorded a high status in the caste hierarchy. Syrian Christian community operates very much as a caste and is properly regarded as a caste or at least a very caste like group.¹⁹ amidst the Hindu society, the saint Thomas Christians of Kerala had inserted themselves within the India caste society by the observance of caste rules and were regarded by the Hindus as a caste occupying a high place within their caste hierarchy.²⁰ ²¹their tradition belief that their ancestors were high caste Hindus such as Nambudiri’s and naris ,who were evangelized by St. Thomas, has also supported their upper caste status.²²

MUSLIMS

Caste system has been observed among Muslims in India.²³they practice endogamy, hypergamy, hereditary occupation, avoid social mixing and have been stratified.²⁴There is some controversy²⁵if these characteristics make them social group or castes of Islam.

Indian Muslims are a mix of Sunni(majority), Shia and others sets of Islam from the earliest days of Islam’s arrival in south Asia, thee Arab, Persian and afghan Muslim have been part of the upper, Nobel caste. Some upper caste Hindus converted to Islam and became part of the governing group of sultanates and Mughal empire, who along with Arabs, Persians and afghans came to be known as Ashraf’s .below them are the middle caste Muslims called ajlaf, and the lowest status is those of the areas.²⁶anti-caste activists like Ambedkar called

¹⁸ Christian castes in encyclopedia Britannica.

¹⁹ Forrester, Duncan b (1980) pg. no 98,102.

²⁰Amaladass, Anand(1993)[1989].dialogue between Hindu and the St. Thomas Christians”.in coward, Harold (ed).Hindu Christian dialogue: perspectives and encounters. Motilal banarsidass. Pg no 14-20

²¹ Bayley (2004),pg. no243-2253

²² FULLER,CHRISTOPHER J. (DEC 1977).”INDIAN CHRISTIANS:POLLUTION AND ORIGINS”.

MAN.NEW.12(3/4):528-529.

²³ Barth, Fredrik (1971). leach, E. R (ed.). aspects of caste in south India, Ceylon, and north-west Pakistan. Cambridge university press .pg no 113.

²⁴ Chaudhary, nandita; anandalakshmy, s;valsiner, Jaan (2013)p. 149

²⁵ Ahmad, Imtiaz (13 may 1967).”the Ashraf and Ajlaf categories in Indo Muslim society. “economic and political weekly.ed2 (19) pg. no 887-891.

²⁶ Bhatta, Zarina(1996).”social stratification among Muslims in India”. In Srinivas.(ed.).caste: its twentieth century avatar. viking pg. no.249-253.

the arzal caste among Muslims as the equivalent of Hindu untouchables,²⁷as did the controversial colonial British ethnographer Herbert hope riley.²⁸similarly ,Christians in Pakistan are called “isai”,meaning followers of isa i.e., Jesus. But the term originates from Hindu caste system and refers to the demeaning jobs performed by Christians in Pakistan out of poverty. Efforts are being made to replace the term with “masihi”, which is preferred by the Christians citizens of Pakistan.²⁹

Endogamy is very common in Muslims in the form of arranged consanguineous marriages among Muslims in India and Pakistan. Malik states that the lack of religious sanction makes qaum a quasi-caste, and something that is found in Islam outside south Asia.³⁰Some assert that the Muslim castes are not as acute in their discrimination as those of the Hindus,³¹while critics of Islam assert that the discrimination in south Asian Muslims society is worse.³²

HISTORY

VEDIC PERIOD (1500-1000 BCE)

During the time of the Rigveda, there were two varnas: ARYA and DASA varna. The distinction originally arose from tribal divisions. The Vedic tribes regarded themselves as arya and the rival tribes were called dasa, dasyu and pani. The dasas were frequent allies of the Aryan tribes, and they were probably assimilated into the Aryan society, given rise to a class distinction.³³many dasa, were however in a servile position, giving rise to the eventual meaning of dasa as servant or slave.³⁴

The Rigvedic society was not distinguished by occupation. Many husband men and artisans practiced a number of crafts. The chariot maker and metal workers enjoyed positions of importance and no stigma was attached to them . similar observations hold for carpenters, tanners, weavers and others.³⁵

Towards the end of the Atharvaveda period, new class distinctions emerged. The erstwhile

²⁷ Ambedkar, bhimrao. Pakistan or the partition of India Thackers publisher.

²⁸ H.h.risley (1903).ethnographic appendices, in GOI, census of india,1901.1CALCUTTA;OFFICE OF THE SUPERINTENDENT OF GOVERNMENT PRINTING.PG NO.45-62.

²⁹ “Pakistan NGO tackles demeaning low caste word for Christians”2 November 2015.archived from the original on 1 December 2016.retreived 30 November 2016.

³⁰ Malik, Jamal(2008).Islam in south Asia: a short history .brill academic pg. no 152-153.

³¹ Madan, t.n.,ed. (1976).Muslim communities of south Asia :culture and society. Vikas publishing house.pg no 114.

³² Ambedkar, Bhimrao, Pakistan or the partition of India. Thackers publishers.

³³ Sharma (1958) pg. no 18

³⁴ Ibid (1958) pg. no 22-23

³⁵ Ibid (1958) pg. no 27-28

Dasas are renamed Shudras, probably to distinguish them from the new meaning of dasa as slave. The Aryas are renamed vis or Vaishya (meaning the members of the tribe) and the new elite classes of Brahmins (priests) and kshatriyas (warriors) are designated as new varnas. The shudras were not only the erstwhile Dasa but also included the aboriginal tribes that were assimilated into the Aryans society as it expanded into genetic settlements.³⁶ There is no evidence of restrictions regarding food and marriage during the Vedic period.³⁷

Later Vedic period(1000-600bce)

In an early Upanishad, Shudra is referred to as Pusan or nourished, suggesting that Shudras were the tillers of the soil.³⁸ but soon afterwards, Shudras are not counted among the tax-payers and they are said to be given away along with the lands when it is gifted.³⁹ The majority of the artisans were also reduced to the position of Shudras, but there is no contempt indicated for their work.⁴⁰ The Brahmins and the kshatriyas are given a special position in the rituals, distinguishing them from both the Vaishya is said to be “oppressed at will” and the Shudra “beaten at will”.⁴¹

Second urbanization (500-200bce)

Our knowledge of this period is supplemented by Pali Buddhist texts. Whereas the Brahmanical texts speak of the four-fold varna system, the Buddhist texts present an alternative picture of the society, stratified along the lines of jathi, kula and occupation. It is likely that the varna system, while being a part of the Brahmanical ideology, was not practically operative in the society.⁴² In the Buddhist text, Brahmin and Ksatriya are described as Jathi rather than varnas. They were in fact the jathis of high rank. The jathis of low rank were mentioned as chandala and occupational class like bamboo weavers, hunters, chariot-makers and seepers. The concepts of Kulas was broadly similar. Along with Brahmins and Kshatriyas, a class called Ganapati (literally householders, but effectively propertied class) was also included among high kulas.⁴³ The people high kulas were engaged in occupations of high ranks, viz., agriculture, trade, cattle-keeping, computing, accounting and writing, and those of low Kulas were engaged in low rank such as basket-weaving and seeping. The Ganapati were an economical class of land-holding agriculturists, who

³⁶ Ibid (1958) pg. no 29-31.

³⁷ Ibid (1958) ,pg. no 40.

³⁸ Ibid (1958) pg. no 44

³⁹ Ibid (1958) pg. no 46-47

⁴⁰ Ibid (1958) pg. no 48

⁴¹ Ibid(1958) pg. no 59-60.

⁴² Chakravarti (1985),pg. no 358.

⁴³ Chakravart i(1985)pg. no 357.

employed dasa-kammakaras(slaves and heard labors)to work on the land . The gahapatis were the primary tax payers of the state. This class was apparently not defined by birth,but by individual economic growth.⁴⁴

Classical period(320-650ce)

The Mahabharata, whose final version is estimated to have been completed by the end of fourth century, discusses the varna system in section 12.181, presenting two models. The first model describes varna as a color-based system, through a character named Bhrigu,” Brahmins varna was white, kshatriyas was red, vaishyas was yellow, and the shudras “black”. This description is questioned by Bharadwaj who says that colors are seen among all there varans,,that desire, anger, fear, greed, grief, anxiety, hunger, and toil prevails over all human being ,that bile and blood flow all human bodies ,so what distinguishes the varnas, he asks. “there is no distinction of varnas. This whole universe is Brahman. It was created formerly by brahma, came to be classified by acts.⁴⁵

Late classical and early medieval period (650 to 1400CE)

Scholars have tried to locate historical evidence for the existence and nature of varna and jathi in document and inscription of medieval India. Supporting evidence for the existence of varna and jathi system in medieval India has been elusive and contradicting evidence has emerged.^{46 47} varna is rarely mentioned in the extensive medieval era records of Andhra Pradesh, for example. This has led Cynthia Talbot, a professor of history and Asian studies, to question whether varna was socially significant in the daily lives of this region. In Tamil Nadu region of India, studied by Leslie Orr, a professor of religion, “Chozha period inscription challenge our ideas about the structuring of (south India) society in general.in contrast to what Brahmanical legal texts may lead us to expect, we do not find that caste is the organizing principle of society or that boundaries between different social groups is sharply demarcated.⁴⁸

Medieval era, Islamic sultanates and Mughal empire period(1000 to1750)

Early and mid-20th century Muslim historians, such as sashimi in 1927 and Qureshi in 1962, proposed that “caste system was established before the arrival of Islam”, and

⁴⁴ Chakravarti (1985)pg. no 359.

⁴⁵ Hildebeitel (2011),pg. no 529-531

⁴⁶ Talbot, precolonial India (2001) pg. no 50-51.

⁴⁷ Orr,leslie (2000).donors,devotees,and daughters of god temple women in medieval tamilnadu.oxford university press.pg. no.30-31.

⁴⁸ Orr,leslie (2000).donors, devotees, and daughter of god temple women in medieval Tamil Nadu. Oxford university Press.pg. no.30.

it and “a nomadic savage lifestyle “in the northwest Indian subcontinent were the primary cause why sindhi non-Muslim armies invaded the region.⁴⁹ According to this hypothesis, the mass conversions occurred from the lower caste Hindus and Mahayana Buddhists who had become “corroded from within by the infiltration of Hindu beliefs and practices”. This theory is now widely believed to be baseless and false.^{50 51}

Later –Mughal period(1700to1850)

Susan Bayly, an anthropologist notes that “caste is not and never has been a fixed fact of Indian life “and the caste system as we know it today, as a ritualized scheme of social stratification, “developed in two stages during the post-mughal period, in 18th and early 19th century. Three sets of value played an important role in this development: priestly hierarchy, kingship, and armed ascetics.⁵² With the Islamic Mughal empire falling apart in the 18th century, regional post mughal ruling geographical and linguistic background attempted to assert their power in different parts of India.⁵³ The “caste ,class, community” structure that formed became valuable in a time when state apparatus was fragmenting, was unreliable and fluid, when rights and life were unpredictable.⁵⁴

Caste politics:

Economic inequality

Economic inequality seems to be related to the influence of inherited social-economic stratification. A 1995 study notes that the caste system in India is a system of exploitation of poor low-ranking groups by more prosperous high ranking groups.⁵⁵ A more prosperous high ranking report published in 2001 note that in India 36.3% of people own no land at all,60.6% own about 15% of land, with a very wealth 3.1% owing 15% of the land.⁵⁶ Indian government has, in addition, vigorously pursued agricultural land ceiling laws which prohibit anyone from owing land greater than mandated limits .India has used this law to forcibly acquire land from some, then redistribute tens of millions of acres to the landless and poor of the low caste. Haque suggest that Indian lawmakers need to reform and

⁴⁹ Maclean, Derry(1997).religion and society in Arab sand netherlands; brill academic publishers pg. no.30-31. ⁵⁰ Eaton, riched(1993).the rise of Islam and Bengal froitier,1204-1760 Berkeley; university of California press.pg. no.117-122.

⁵¹ Maclean, derry(1997).religion and society in Arab sind. Netherlands ;brill academic publishers.pg. no.31-34,49-50.

⁵² Bayley (2001) pg. no 25-28

⁵³ Bayley (2001) pg. no.29-30

⁵⁴ Bayley (2001) pg. no.31.

⁵⁵ Indian-a country study, study, us library of congress,1995,

⁵⁶ Rural poverty report 2001-the challenge of ending rural poverty archived 24 September 2015 at the wayback machine, chapter 3 pg. no 77.

modernize the nation's land laws and rely less on blind adherence to land ceiling and tenancy reforms.⁵⁷ For specific evidence, Aiyar mentions the following.

Critics believe that the economic liberalization has benefited just a small elite and left behind the poor, especially the lowest Hindu caste of Dalits. But a recent authoritative survey revealed striking improvements in living standards of Dalits in the last two decades. Television ownership was up from zero to 45 percent; cellphone ownership was up from zero to 36 percent; two-wheeler ownership up from zero to 12.3 percent; children eating yesterday's leftovers down from 95.9 percent to 16.2 percent; Dalits running their own business up from 6 percent to 37 percent; and proportion working as agricultural laborer's down from 46.1 percent to 20.5 percent.

Apartheid and discrimination

Sociologists Kevin Reilly, Stephen Kaufman and Angela Bodino, while critical of the caste system, conclude that modern India does not practice apartheid since there is no state-sanctioned discrimination.⁵⁹ They write that casteism in India is presently "as well as tribal people and members of the lowest caste in India benefit from broad affirmative action programs and are enjoying greater political powers."⁶⁰ A hypothesis that caste amounts to race has been rejected by some scholars.⁶¹ Ambedkar, for example, wrote that "the Brahmin of Punjab is racially of the same stock as the chamber of Punjab. The caste system does not demarcate racial division of people of the same race." Various sociologists, anthropologists and historians have rejected the racial origins and racial emphasis of caste and consider the idea to be one that has purely political and economic undertones. Beteille writes that "the scheduled castes of India taken together are no more a race than are the Brahmins taken together. Every social group cannot be regarded as a race simply because we want to protect it against prejudice and discrimination", and that the 2001 Durban conference on racism hosted by the U.N. is "turning its back on established scientific opinion."

CASE LAW:

1) Muslim Vs dalit in Tamil Nadu

This case was held in a village called Bomminayakanur in the district of Theni in the date of

⁵⁷ Hans tad (2005). "improving land access to India's rural poor".

⁵⁸ Hoque (2006). "improving the rural poor's access to land in India".

⁵⁹ Kevin Reilly, Stephen Kaufman, Angela Bodino, Racism: a global reader pg. no 21, M.E. Sharpe, 2003.

⁶⁰ Excerpts from the constitution of India.

⁶¹ Ambedkar. (1979). The annihilation of caste. Writing and speeches education department, government of Maharashtra. pg. no. 49

April 24 2018.in village there is a caste called Dalit the day the person was dead in that village .so they went for the funeral rites .by the way they want to go to the funeral rites another death was held in that village so they take another ways to the rituals the another ways is belongs to the Muslims people i. e there are many families in Muslims caste lived in the place. When the JINAZE (dead body) is coming into the Muslims place they people said that the jianzi do wants to come into the place, not only the jianzi the other caste (Dalit) is not come to that place. The problems raised there then the police used to come there and solved the problems. This issue was held in April 24 2018.On 5th may the Muslim boy of that village has a coconut garden the boy usually wants to go with other oration that day the boy went by the Dalits caste people said area. The caste people not allowed the boy to enter into the area because on that funeral rites they caste people not allowed them so that, they beaten the boy because of that issue. Then it becomes to the caste problems. There are 50 families and houses are destroyed in that area, the both the caste members fighting by through the things of the others caste people. The police tried to control the problems. The major issue is happening in Tamil Nadu that is the government is not providing the valid instrument for a issues like a head tire. So, in that situation the Tamil Nadu police is wearing a bike helmet because the problem is heavy .like they are firing the houses of the both the caste, throwing the things outside ,using roads, etc. The police used to stop the problems and the damages is 50 houses destroyed,13 people are struggling in the hospitals and so on. This is the case based on the caste in Muslims and Dalits in Theni district.

2) TWO DALITS MURDERED BY ASSAILANTS BELONGING TO THEVAR COMMUNITY NEAR TUTICORIN IN TAMIL NADU.

In Chennai the specter of oppression against Dalits reared its ugly head in the southern Tamil Nadu district of Tuticorin where two Dalit men were murdered by non-dalits assailants on Friday late night, sources said. The victims were identified as A. PALAVESAM,60 and his kin, R. THANGARAJ,26 OF underclaim village, about 45 km from tuticorin. According to preliminary inquiries, Palavesam had lodged a police complaint against a moneylender shanmugasundaram, belonging to thevar community, from whom the complainant had borrowed money by pledging his property documents about a year ago. Palavesam claimed he had repaid the principal amount with interest and met shanmugasundaram, who belong to a neighboring village, on Thursday, to demand his document back. At the time, shanmugasundaram and his accomplices allegedly assaulted palavesam and abused him citing his caste. Based on palavesam's complaint Nazareth police registered a case against shanmugasundaram under section of the scheduled caste and

scheduled tribe(prevention of atrocities act).he was subsequently arrested and remanded in judicial custody. Infuriated over the arrest, shanmugasundaram kin and members of the community, armed with lethal weapons, barged into the house of palavesam and murdered him and his thangaraj before fleeing from the place. Three assailants have been arrested in connection with the murder. A hunt is on for others. A large posse of police personnel have been deployed in the village to avert further untoward incidents.⁶²

3) Chennai: electrician held in AIADMK functionary murder case:

Vinayaka is also an AIADMK functionary and is a member of the MGR Peravai. A 40-year-old electrician was on Saturday arrested in connection with the murder of an AIADMK functionary kottaisamy at red hills on sep 6,2015. In Chennai 40 years old electrician was on Saturday arrested in connection with the murder of an AIADMK functionary kottaisamy at red hills last Sunday. The accused, nagaraj ,is a resident of the same area and was picked up from his hideout by a special team, police said with nagaraj's arrest ,the total number of those held in connection with the murder has increased to 11.kottaisamy,a former president of Nallor panchayat, and joint secretary of amma peravai, sholavaram unit was a resident of solaiyamman nagar 8th street. He was drinking with his friends when he was hacked to death by a gang. A day after the murder, police arrested six persons including nallor panchayat president, vinayagam(40),who was angered over kottaisamy's clout in the locality. Further, he was also not happy with kottaisamy flourishing in real estate business, the police saidvinayakam is also an AIADMK functionary and is a member of the MGR peravai." we have arrested 11 out of the 15 suspects so far' said by senior police officer.⁶³

In present day culture of cast:

In April 2006 originating more than 2,500 years ago as varnashrama dharma, a theory of social rank, the caste system in India entails that people are born into certain castes. A person's caste, known as jati, is not a matter of choice but is fixed on the basis of birth. This system of graded inequality has the sanction of religion formulated by Brahmans, who assigned for themselves the top position in today known as Hinduism, a term that has come to be used only the last 300 years. Till date, India is the only country where we can find segregated settlements for so called untouchable castes, who today prefer to call themselves Dalits. Social apartheid can easily be witnessed in India villages, where 70 percent

⁶² Mumbai mirror. Retrieved on June 27, 2020

⁶³ Deccan chronicle.com. Retrieved on June 27, 2020

of the nation's population lives. Herein most cases, the Dalits have no access to common properties of the village temples, common lands, burial ground, common wells, etc. every aspect of public life for Dalits is separated, segregated. According to statistics released by the government of India, every hour two Dalits women are raped, every day two Dalits are murdered; every day two Dalits houses are burnt.

In India, people are quick to know the other person's caste; the full name of the person, the accent of the local language, place of origin, profession, dress, caste markers worn on the body are some of the various ways in which it is deciphered. In the personal sphere, caste inflects marriage, food habits, the circle of friends, the use of language, etc. invariably, the personal spills over into the public sphere, caste, thus, remains visible yet invisible. The invisible is rendered visible socially, culturally, politically and economically. Sometimes, even when people convert to other religions, they carry with them the caste distinctions. For instance, people self-identify themselves as Brahmin Christians, eddy Christians and Dalit Christians. However, in Islam, which has a significant presence in India, caste categories are more firmly obliterated.⁶⁴

Criticism:

There has been criticism of the caste system from both within and outside of India.⁶⁵ since the 1980s, caste has become a major issue in the politics of India.⁶⁶

Indian social reformers

The caste system has been criticized by many Indian social reformers.

Basava

Basava (1105-1167) arguably one of the first social reformers, Basava championed devotional worship that rejected temple worship and rituals and replaced it with personalized direct worship of Shiva through practices such as individually worn icons and symbols like a small linga. This approach brought Shiva's presence to everyone and at all times, without gender, class or caste discrimination. His teachings and verses such as *kayakave kailasa* became popular.

Jyoti Rao Phule

Jyoti Rao Phule (1827-1890) vehemently cruised any explanation that the caste system was natural and ordained by the creator in Hindu texts. If brahma wanted

⁶⁴ The power of culture.

⁶⁵ India's caste system discriminates archived 20 april2006 at the wayback machine.

⁶⁶ Aditya nigam." caste politics in India "archived from the original on 28 august 2005.retrived 11 June 2020

castes, argued Phule, he would have ordained the same for others creatures. There are no castes in species of animals or birds, so why should there be one among human animals.⁶⁷

Vivekananda

Vivekananda similarly criticized caste as one of the many human institution that bars the powers of free thought and action of an individual. Caste or no caste, creed or no creed, any man, or class, or caste, or nation, or institution that bars the power of free through and bars action of an individuals is devilish, and must go down. Liberty of thought and action, asserted Vivekananda, is the only condition of life, of growth and of well-being.⁶⁸

B.R. Ambedkar

B.R. Ambedkar was born in a caste that was classified as untouchable, became a leader of human rights campaigns in India, a prolific writer, and a key person in drafting modern India's constitution in the 1940s. He wrote extensively on discrimination, trauma and what he saw as the tragic effects of the caste system in India. He believed that the caste system originated in the practice of endogamy and that it spread through imitation by other groups. He wrote that initially, Brahmins, kshatriyas, Vaishyas and Shudras existed as classes whose choice of occupation was not restricted by birth and in which exogamy was prevalent. Brahmins then began to practice endogamy and enclosed themselves, hence Ambedkar defines caste as "enclosed class". He believed that traditions such as sati, enforced widowhood and child marriage developed from the need to reinforce endogamy and shastras were used to glorify these practices so that they are observed without being questioned. Later, other caste groups imitated these customs. However, although Ambedkar uses the approach of psychologist Gabriel Tarde to indicate how the caste system spread, he also explains that Brahmins or Manu cannot be blamed for the origin of the caste system and he discredits theories which trace the origin of caste system in races.⁶⁹

Conclusion:

The caste system had great effects on the Indian society. Despite the fact that it's one of the many types of segregation seen throughout India, it did have its beneficial qualities. For instance, it did establish a stable social order in the country for quite some time until an official government came into place. All of the Indian's people played a role in their society and had certain jobs. The former caste members are now more tolerant of other castes and

⁶⁷ Singh and roy (2011) Indian political thought; themes and thinkers.pearson.pg no 82-90.

⁶⁸ Swami Vivekananda (1952) the complete works of swami Vivekananda (8 vols, Calcutta).v.pg no 25-30

⁶⁹ Ambedkar,dr.b.r.pritchett, frances(ed)."caste in india;their mechanism, genesis, and development".

sub-caste people, and the division in the society are gradually diminishing.